

WP4: Develop systems and behavioral based ToCs to understand the potential impact of public and private interventions

D4.1

Methodological brief

ENFASYS

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List of abbreviations

CAP	Common Agriculture Policy
CF	Conceptual Framework
CLD	Causal Loop Diagram
CS	Case Study
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
JRC	Joint Research Committee
MLP	Multi Level Perspective
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
RESET	Realize, Energize, Soothe, End unproductive thinking, Talk it out
SFS	Sustainable Farming Systems
SMART	Specific Measurable Attainable Relevant Time-bound
SSBC	Self-regulated Stage model of Behaviour Change
ToC	Theory of Change
VNM	Value Network Map
WS	Workshop
WP	Working Package

Executive summary

The purpose of this methodological brief is to provide guidance on **HOW to study** the **WHAT** of the ENFASYS project. While the "WHAT" is outlined in the ENFASYS conceptual framework, the "HOW" is addressed in this brief:

How can ENFASYS support societal actors to understand and address lock-ins that constrain transitions to resilient and sustainable agriculture across scales - towards sustainable agricultural systems?

To answer this question, this brief develops a methodological framework for mapping systems across scales. This processual account of systems mapping across scales supports research teams in bridging the gap between systemic and behavioural methodologies. As such, systems mapping across scales provides a framework for actionable interdisciplinary research. One that takes into account the different perspectives of the research team and stakeholders. Different scales of analysis and action. And how temporality affects both to achieve the ENFASYS goals.

This is presented in the four sections of the brief:

Section 1 provides an overview of the ENFASYS project. It's key components, objectives and the organization of the work.

Section 2 introduces the concepts underlying the ENFASYS methodological framework: systems thinking, systems mapping, and systems change.

Section 3 focuses on the application of the systems mapping approach within the ENFASYS framework. It outlines the flow of activities across WPs, scales, and time. It does so by presenting the perspectives of the coordinator, the WP leader, and the CS coordinators.

Section 4 summarizes the key points of the methodological framework. It highlights the importance of stakeholder engagement across scales and over time.

1 Project objectives and organization of the work

ENFASYS is a Research and Innovation Action project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme. It aims to stimulate a just and fair transition to sustainable farming systems (SFS) by improving policies and business strategies to encourage farmers to change their production systems. The project acknowledges that farmers face multiple lock-ins in current food systems, which hinder their transition to more sustainable practices. To overcome these challenges, ENFASYS focuses on strengthening both public strategies (policies) and private strategies (business models, social innovations) to support the Green Deal and Farm to Fork ambitions.

To achieve its goals, ENFASYS prioritizes four key objectives:

- 1 It aims to gain a better understanding of the lock-ins and levers in agri-food systems. This involves identifying the barriers that prevent farmers from adopting sustainable practices and exploring potential solutions.
- 2 ENFASYS seeks to understand the behavioural drivers of farmers, consumers, and other actors in the food chain. By understanding the motivations and behaviours of key stakeholders, the project can develop targeted interventions.
- 3 ENFASYS aims to generate more and better evidence on the potential effectiveness of interventions. This involves conducting research and experiments to evaluate the impact of different strategies and interventions.
- 4 The project emphasizes the need for a structured approach to linking knowledge to action, ensuring that research findings translate into practical actions and policy recommendations.

To guide the research and ensure coherence and consistency, ENFASYS has developed an overarching methodological framework. This framework provides a comprehensive and integrated approach to collecting, analysing, and interpreting data. It promotes cross-disciplinary research approaches, enhancing the validity and reliability of findings (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Overview of the ENFASYS project: systems view to large scale transformation towards SFS (Marchand et al. 2019)

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The methodological framework provides guidance on how the project will study and address the complex challenges of transitioning to sustainable farming systems by adopting a systems thinking approach.

Systems thinking is a holistic and problem-oriented approach that integrates scientific, behavioral, and systemic analysis to understand and address complex problems.

It embraces complexity without getting overwhelmed by it and creates spaces for participation among societal actors to support their understanding and action on these problems (Williams & Shepherd, 2016).

In Figure 2 we can see an example of a systems thinking approach to factors affecting sustainable yield increases in Afghanistan (Samadi, 2013).

Figure 2 Example of a systems thinking approach to factors affecting sustainable yield increases in Afghanistan (Samadi, 2013).

One tool used within systems thinking is systems mapping.

Systems mapping involves creating visual depictions such as diagrams, maps, or sketched models to represent the complex relationships between multiple actors and issues (Sedlacko et al. 2014).

This tool brings systems thinking into participatory spaces and is particularly useful in triggering and supporting socio-ecological transformations, such as those aimed for by the ENFASYS project.

In line with this, we have developed systems map of the methodological framework of ENFASYS. This approach allows us to guide the research process across work packages that have different methodologies and belong to different disciplines.

By utilizing systems mapping, we ensure the validity and reliability of findings across stakeholder engagement, co-design processes, and experimental research, making the research outcomes context-specific and relevant to the needs and perspectives of the stakeholders involved.

This report is organized into four sections, each focusing on different aspects of the methodological framework:

Section 1: Project Objectives and Organization of the Work This section provides an overview of the ENFASYS project and its key components. It highlights the project's objectives, which include gaining a better understanding of the lock-ins and levers in agri-food systems, understanding the behavioural drivers of key stakeholders, generating evidence on the effectiveness of interventions, and linking knowledge to action. The section also outlines the organization of the project, with nine work packages focusing on different research objectives.

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Section 2: General Methodological Considerations In this section, we delve into the concepts of systems thinking and systems mapping, which are the foundation of the ENFASYS methodological framework. We explain how systems thinking provides a holistic and problem-oriented approach to understanding complex problems, and how systems mapping is used as a tool within this approach to visually represent the relationships and interdependencies within a system. We discuss how systems thinking and system mapping inform decision-makers in both the public and private sectors, and how they are used as a strategic toolkit for transforming the food and agriculture sector.

Section 3: Application of Systems Mapping in ENFASYS This section focuses on the application of systems mapping within the ENFASYS project. We provide a roadmap of the methodological framework, outlining the flow of activities and deliverables for each work package. We discuss the different phases of the project, including sensemaking, envisioning, synthesis, iteration, and (re)envisioning. We also highlight the scalar perspective of the methodology, which considers the different levels of analysis and action within the project.

Section 4: Conclusion In the conclusion, we summarize the key points of the methodological framework and highlight the importance of collaboration and engagement with stakeholders in the project. We emphasize the role of the methodological frameworks developed within each work package in guiding the research process and ensuring the validity and reliability of the findings. We also discuss the significance of long-term engagement with stakeholders for the successful implementation and impact of the research.

1.1 Systems perspective on the work across scales: integrated view on the levels of analysis

The ENFASYS project consists of nine work packages (WPs) that span over a period of 48 months. Each WP focuses on specific research objectives and activities that contribute to the overall goal of enabling a just and fair transition to sustainable farming systems (SFS). As such research activities are unfolding on multiple scales.

It is important to understand that the concept of scale is used in ENFASYS to raise awareness of the hierarchical and vertical relations that structure socio-spatial processes (levels of governance, stages of the value chain as opposed to relations based on territory, place, or network).

In WP1, the project starts by scoping and framing pathways towards SFS, leveraging state-of-the-art research and ongoing projects to inform the project's direction. Building on the scoping work in WP1, WP2 aims to develop a system dynamic understanding of mechanisms, lock-ins, and levers within the broader food system. This is achieved through CS research and scaling up to a system dynamic model for evaluation. In WP3, the focus shifts to comprehending the behavioural factors that influence farmers' decision-making and understanding the buying behaviour of products from SFS. This is done through cross-case analyses and surveys as the main data sources.

WP4 plays a critical role in providing a methodological framework that integrates the findings from WP2 and WP3. The framework ensures a balanced mixed methods approach for developing systems- and behavioural-based theories of change (ToCs).

To test the potential of interventions, WP5 conducts experimental studies and system dynamic modelling. The results from these studies feed into WP4 and WP7, contributing to the development of effective strategies and recommendations. In WP6, the focus is on enhancing policy design and implementation to foster the shift towards SFS. This involves analysing existing policies, identifying gaps, and proposing strategies for policy improvement.

WP7 is dedicated to developing business strategies, models, and social innovations that incentivize farmers to transition towards SFS. This includes exploring innovative approaches to drive sustainable practices and engagement within the agricultural sector. WP8 takes on the important task of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. This includes the development of an online course, a website, and capacity building initiatives to share the project's findings and knowledge with key target groups.

To ensure effective coordination and risk mitigation throughout the project, each WP has a lead and co-lead who work together to drive the research objectives forward. Overall, the collaboration between the different work packages in the ENFASYS project creates a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach to address the complex challenges of transitioning to sustainable farming systems.

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This internal coherence is insured with the two overarching documents of the ENFASYS project:

The conceptual framework (CF) which provides a comprehensive understanding of the research topic and guides the research by defining key concepts and their relationships. It supports the consideration of systems thinking, behavioural factors, public interventions, and private interventions to transition towards more sustainable food systems.

The methodological framework focuses on how to conduct the research within the ENFASYS project. It provides overview of the methodologies, analytical frameworks, and scales of analysis or action used in the project. It complements the conceptual framework by specifying the research methods and approaches to be employed.

For this reason, in what follows we present perspectives of actors that works across the scales of ENFASYS project with the scope of providing a shared understanding on the work done in each WP that encompasses collaborative work of both the CS coordinators and the WP teams.

2 General methodological considerations

In this section, we introduce the general methodological considerations of the ENFASYS project, which includes the use of systems mapping as an overarching methodological approach.

We use systems mapping as an overarching methodological approach to the ENFASYS project to obtain insights, enable reflection and foster knowledge sharing. Systems mapping consists of creating visual depictions such as diagrams, maps or sketched models of a complex system by depicting an entangled set of relationships and feedback loops among actors and trends (Sedlacko et al., 2014; Waddell, 2016).

The methodological approach of systems mapping is applied across different scales and levels of analysis within the ENFASYS project. It helps stakeholders understand the specific dynamics and challenges within their own farming systems, as well as the broader dynamics and interactions within the food and agriculture systems.

By visually representing the relationships and interdependencies, systems mapping facilitates communication, collaboration, and the co-creation of strategies and initiatives.

2.1 Systems mapping to guide systems thinking in ENFASYS

Systems mapping in ENFASYS is a methodology that engages multiple stakeholders in the European Union Agri-Food Sector to understand and address complex challenges across scales. Through a sequence of exercises, including sensemaking of problems and actors, envisioning solutions, and reconfiguring actors, it aims to alter networks and tackle common problems. This iterative process involves different stakeholder groups across 12 case studies in Europe.

The goal of systems mapping in the ENFASYS project is to define specific combinations of actors, resources, and activities that can work together to address complex problems simultaneously. By identifying disconnected sub-components within a system and assessing how to bridge those gaps, participants across the value chain, including policy makers, researchers, and local farmers, can collectively determine how to combine resources and networks to address the identified problems.

Systems mapping for systems change unfolds in several steps:

- 1 We use visual representations like causal loop diagrams and value network maps to maps (VNMs) to map the interrelated elements of the systems: the problems and the actors (Manyise et al., 2024).
- 2 We engage in participatory process of systems mapping that involve co-creation of conceptual models and the engagement of actors closely associated with the system (Dentoni & Roglic, 2024).
- 3 We collaboratively construct a causal map of the system of interest in our case of the overall workflow of ENFASYS, or the problems and the actors associated with them within the case studies, using factors and their causal connections.
- 4 We collect additional information, such as the strength of the causal connections, important factors, controllable factors or vulnerable factors to enhance the map.
- 5 We consider the limitations of participatory processes of systems mapping, such as capturing group-level outcomes, cultural and contextual suitability and the influence on policy or organizational decisions (Barbrook-Johnson and Penn, 2021).

In Figure 3 we present this stepwise approach to participatory systems mapping that we use across scales within the ENFASYS project.

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Figure 3 Systems mapping for systems change (Dentoni et al. 2022)

Systems change, as pursued in the ENFASYS project, refers to the intentional and purposeful alteration of networks and interactions within farming systems to address the complex problems identified in the sensemaking phase and achieve the desired outcomes outlined in the envisioning phase. This change involves understanding the interconnectedness of various sub-components within the system, such as commodities, local practices, and pedoclimatic zones, and their relationships to the larger European Union Agri-food system.

An important characteristic of systems mapping, particularly as it is operationalized in ENFASYS is that it is used across different scales. Scales here refer to socio-spatial dimensions and include concepts of place, territory, and space. Scales are not fixed attributes but dynamic processes involving connections and interactions between different levels of analysis (Chatterjee et al., 2023).

Moving between different scales of analysis is essential for understanding the socio-spatial relationships underlying the transition to sustainable farming systems.

Scale, in this context, refers to the hierarchical and vertical relations that structure socio-spatial processes, such as governance levels and stages in the value chain.

By considering these scales, we can better comprehend the interconnectedness and interactions between different levels of analysis.

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It is important to note that scales are not fixed attributes but dynamic processes that involve connections and interactions across different levels. This understanding of scales allows us to adopt a system mapping approach that includes linkages and interactions across scales, creating a comprehensive framework for understanding the complexities of the transition to sustainable farming systems and envision and test the enactment of systems change.

Systems change is a self-organizing and emergent process in which actors across different scales purposefully alter their interactions and networks to bring about transformation.

Systems mapping, as a participatory process, supports systems change by engaging multiple actors and facilitating collective agency for change. This analytical underpinning of the ENFASYS methodological framework allows for a comprehensive understanding and effective addressing of complex challenges in the European Union Agri-Food Sector.

2.1.1 How system thinking and system mapping practices inform public and private decision makers

System thinking and system mapping practices inform public and private decision-makers by providing a holistic and integrated perspective on the complex challenges of food and agriculture systems.

System thinking helps decision-makers to identify and analyse the causal relationships and feedback loops within a system, enabling them to better understand the potential impacts of their decisions. It encourages decision-makers to understand the interconnectedness and interdependencies of different components within the system.

System mapping, on the other hand, provides visual representations of these relationships, helping decision-makers to identify leverage points, feedback loops, and potential interventions. As such it can help navigate trade-offs between urgency and inclusivity in scaling innovations. System mapping techniques, such as cognitive mapping, allow decision-makers to visually represent and communicate the complex relationships and interdependencies within a system, facilitating a shared understanding among stakeholders.

In the public sector, system thinking, and system mapping can inform the development of policies and strategies that address complex societal and environmental challenges, such as sustainable agriculture and environmental conservation (Levy et al. 2018).

In the private sector, these practices can support strategic planning, risk assessment, and innovation by providing insights into the interconnectedness of various factors and stakeholders within a business ecosystem (Barbrook-Johnson and Penn, 2021).

By adopting a systems perspective, decision-makers can better understand the underlying causes of problems and identify effective solutions. They can consider the broader implications and unintended consequences of their decisions, as well as the potential interactions between different actors and sectors within the system. This enables more informed and strategic decision-making, leading to more effective policy designs and business strategies supporting transformations across scales.

2.1.2 How systems thinking and system mapping are used as a strategic toolkit for transforming food and agriculture from the bottom up

Systems thinking and system mapping are used as a strategic toolkit for transforming food and agriculture from the bottom up by empowering stakeholders across scales to actively participate in the transformation process. These approaches allow decision makers to understand the complex interrelationships and feedback loops within a system, which is crucial for effective decision making.

By using participatory systems mapping, decision makers can collaboratively construct causal maps that capture the various factors and their causal connections within a system (Wilkinson et al., 2021). This process helps to identify the contextual social, political, and external drivers that influence the system, enabling decision makers to consider a broader range of factors and potential impacts. By visualizing the complexity of the food and agriculture systems,

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system mapping helps stakeholders to collectively understand the systemic challenges and identify potential solutions (Wright, 2012).

By engaging in systems thinking, stakeholders can identify the underlying causes of unsustainable practices and develop interventions that address those root causes. System mapping provides a shared language and platform for collaboration, allowing stakeholders to co-create strategies and initiatives that drive transformative change.

This strategic toolkit therefore ensures that the transformation process is inclusive, participatory, and context specific. It enables stakeholders to articulate their visions, goals, and priorities, and facilitates the coordination and alignment of efforts across different levels of analysis, from farm-level to regional, national, and even European levels.

2.1.3 How systems thinking and systems mapping are used for envisioning systems change

Systems thinking and system mapping are used for envisioning systems change at different levels of analysis.

At the farm-level, stakeholders can use systems thinking and system mapping to understand the specific dynamics and challenges within their own farming systems. This allows them to envision and design interventions that promote sustainable and resilient practices, aligning with their own goals and objectives.

At the regional, national, and European levels, systems thinking, and system mapping provide a framework for understanding the broader dynamics and interactions within the food and agriculture systems. This enables stakeholders to identify systemic barriers, leverage points, and potential interventions that can drive systemic change. It allows for a comprehensive understanding of the interrelationships between different actors, sectors, policies, and market dynamics, informing the development of integrated strategies and policies.

By envisioning systems change at different levels of analysis, stakeholders can align their efforts, share knowledge and experiences, and coordinate actions to achieve transformative outcomes across scales.

In summary, the ENFASYS project adopts a system thinking approach to enable a just and fair transition to sustainable farming systems. Systems mapping serves as a tool within this approach, allowing for the visual representation of complex relationships and the identification of specific combinations of actors, resources, and activities to address these challenges. Through an iterative and participatory process, systems change is pursued to alter networks and interactions within farming systems with the objective to lead to a transformative impact on the European Union Agri-food system.

3 Application of systems mapping in ENFASYS

Systems mapping in the ENFASYS project provides methodological approach to understand and address complex challenges in the context of sustainable farming systems. Its application in that regard is threefold:

- 1 **Understanding system dynamics:** Systems mapping helps in understanding the complex interrelationships and feedback loops within the farming system. It allows stakeholders to analyse the drivers and constraints of the system, identifying potential leverage points for intervention.
- 2 **Identifying key actors and resources:** Through systems mapping, ENFASYS can identify the specific combinations of actors, resources, and activities that contribute to sustainable farming systems. This information helps in designing targeted interventions and resource allocation.
- 3 **Visual representation of relationships:** Systems mapping provides a visual representation of the relationships between different components of the farming system.

This section describes the processual (roadmap) and scalar perspectives of this work across ENFASYS research work packages delineating the work done by the research teams as WP leads, CS coordinators and the engagement with the stakeholders across scales.

3.1 Roadmap of the ENFASYS methodological framework

A detailed map and the evolution of the methodological framework are available on the MIRO board:

<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMcx-tz8=/>

Figure 4 Methodological flow of the ENFASYS project

To foster a shared understanding of the overall methodological workflow of the ENFASYS project we build processual systems map that delineates activities unfolding in five phases: (1) sensemaking, (2) envisioning, (3)

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synthesizing, (4) iterating and (5) envisioning. Its scope is to present the overview of the ENFASYS activities based on inputs collected from all task leaders on the following topics:

- What methodologies do we adopt in the ENFASYS project?
- What knowledge and data will be shared?
- With whom will the data and the knowledge be shared?
- When will the data and knowledge be shared?
- In what format will the data and knowledge be shared?

The methodological framework builds on the conceptual framework that has been developed in T1.1 that gives guidance on **WHAT** to study within the ENFASYS project. This document provides guidelines on **HOW to study** the **WHAT**, i.e. an implementable work plan within the ENFASYS project.

WP leaders and CS coordinators use the framework as a reference point on what they deliver, to whom and for what purpose.

We use systems mapping as an overarching methodological approach to the ENFASYS project to obtain insights, enable reflection and foster knowledge sharing. Systems mapping consists of creating visual depictions such as diagrams, maps or sketched models of a complex system by depicting an entangled set of relationships and feedback loops among actors and trends (Sedlacko et al., 2014; Waddell, 2016).

3.1.1 Processual account of the workflow: phases

Within the framework of the ENFASYS project, systems mapping is a general approach to collectively understand *how complex problems and socio-ecological systems relate to each other* (Senge, 2007) and to collectively envision *how to address these problems through processes of systems change* (Dentoni et al., 2023).

In this sense that we understand the methodological framework of ENFASYS as unfolding through

- Phase 1: Make sense of the grand challenge, such as transitioning towards carbon-neutral farming systems (**sensemaking**). Understanding reality with societal actors.
- Phase 2: Reconfigure networks to better address the grand challenges (**envisioning**). Deliberating and negotiating change with societal actors to identify the leverage points for change.
- Phase 3: Synthesis is how one or more interventions are causally connected to address the grand challenge (**synthesizing**). Building narratives to influence policymakers and business actors.
- Phase 4: Iterate the results from the phases 1-3 at the CS and systemic level to makes sense of and identify complementary actors, resources, and strategies (**iterating**).
- Phase 5: Develop propositions for the systemic change of the farming systems (**re-envisioning**).

With this understanding of systems mapping, the methodological framework of ENFASYS can be defined as a system mapping process of the farming systems at a landscape and a case-study level as such it provides a roadmap showing how and why a selection of methodologies and analytical frameworks are to be fit together and operationalized to reach the project's objectives.

3.1.1.1 Phase 1: sensemaking

In this respect, **the sensemaking in phase one** is guided by the development of the conceptual framework and the findings of the four literature reviews (T1.1) that examine the state of play in policy, behaviours, business, and system dynamics. The light touch review (T1.3) also provides insights on the diversity of transformation and innovation initiatives based on their scale, mode and scope (to T1.2); contextualization of in-depth case studies and general insights on how to change (to T4.2) as well as the insights on implemented policy designs (T6.1) and business strategies (T7.1) and the existing gaps. Mapping and surveying of the stakeholder ecosystem (T2.1) allow for a cross-case analysis of food system mechanisms that identify lock-ins, levers and interventions that feed into the cross-case systems based ToCs (T4.2) along with surveys on behavioural factors (T3.2) that also inform policy and business interventions in the iteration phase (T6.2 and T7.2) as well as give insights on interventions to be tested in lab in field

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at case level (T5.3). Choice experiments to identify end market opportunities (T3.3) provide insights on the effect of interventions to T6.2 and T7.2 in the iterations phase. Lastly, randomized trials on nudging farmers (T5.1) complement the work of T3.2 with the insight on the interventions to be tested in lab in the field at CS level (T5.3) in the iterations phase.

Thus, WP1 sets the scene conceptually and empirically for the task leaders of WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP7 that is operationalized through a common methodological framework (T4.1). In addition, all WP tasks follow the multi-stakeholder protocol (T9.3), the horizontal implementation of which ensures the involvement of different actors and the dissemination of ENFASYS research findings to various interest groups such as farmers' groups, advisors, companies, NGOs, and other actors within the food system, considering their perspective on the adoption and implementation of ENFASYS research findings and recommendations.

After the overarching work of framing the context and operationalizing it, the WP2 engages in the analysis of ten pre-selected case studies that represent diverse lock-in conditions, according to the diversity of farming systems, value-chain and governance settings; different strategies at the business and marketing side and the wide range of instruments in the policy side strategies to overcome lock-ins. We map and survey the stakeholder ecosystem (T2.1) and identify the behavioural factors influencing readiness for potential intervention towards sustainable farming systems (SFS) in a participatory manner (T3.1). T2.1 will also identify policy environment, governance networks and value chain configurations that will feed into the cross-case analysis of food system mechanisms (T2.2).

In parallel, drawing on all types of interventions identified by the literature review and an a priori assessment by the CS coordinators on whether certain interventions could work “in practice”, T3.1 will produce a cross-case synthesis of *CS level* mapping the scoped interventions based on the behavioural readiness of relevant actors (incl. consumers, farmers, and food system actors) to adapt to the interventions. Within this task, the CS coordinators will be trained to organize workshops with stakeholders identified in T2.1 in their CS context with the scope to identify behavioural factors likely to impact the effectiveness and acceptability of different types of interventions across other actors and in different settings. This will result in some hypotheses of which interventions (or which combinations of interventions) could work.

Building on the work of T3.1 the most promising interventions targeting farmers and consumers will be selected for each case country from a behavioural science of point of view. Surveys will be designed by the task leader and back-translated and distributed by the CS coordinators within the CS (~30 respondents per case) and across the wider community (~200-500) to identify the behavioural readiness levels of farmers towards the selected interventions (T3.2). For consumers, equally, surveys and discrete choice experiments (T3.3) will be designed at the CS country level. These experiments will target 12-15 countries with 800-1200 consumers per country to identify opportunities for innovative policy and business strategies based on identified: market-segments, and end markets. A separate online experiment with 150-200 consumers will be conducted in each case country to identify tensions between consumers' stated willingness to pay and their intended shopping behaviour, potentially highlighting alternative routes to engage citizen-consumers in SFS transitions (T3.3).

Randomized trials on nudging farmers toward the adoption of SFS (T5.1) are performed based on the same sample of farmers from T3.2 (T5.1) feeding from the theory identified in the conceptual framework (T1.1) and practices identified by the light touch review (T1.3). Farmers are exposed to nudges that test the impact of information, education, and group pressure-based intervention types on farmers' participation in voluntary schemes.

The identified policy environment, governance networks, value chain configurations, key actors (T2.1 and T2.2) and behavioural factors (T3.2) along with the mapping of the potential opportunities for innovative policy and business strategies (T3.3) form the foundation for the envisioning process in phase two. The results of the nudge experiments consist of a classification (T5.1) that will feed the second envisioning process (phase 5).

3.1.1.2 Phase 2: envisioning

The envisioning process in phase two focuses on playing the scales by co-designing policy and business strategies (T6.1 and T7.1) by involving actors that operate in the national or even EU-space. It considers the case studies in relation to national and EU policy frameworks and nationally or transnationally operating value chains.

We qualitatively envision/design policy mixes and business strategies to overcome lock-in (T6.1 and T7.1). To do so, we build on types of policies and business models identified in the literature (T1.1) and during the light touch

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review (T1.3). These insights (T1.1 and T1.3) are coupled with the information on the key actors (T2.1) and the behavioural factors (T3.1), as well as the cross-case analysis of food system mechanisms (T2.2). Using these insights, the CS coordinators are trained (T6.1 and T7.1) to organize a process at the CS level that will allow them to: 1) develop a shared understanding of lock-ins and formulate SMART goals for the farming systems; 2) collect possible measures and policy tools to support desired development; 3) combine goals and policies into a policy mix and assess its coherence, consistency, congruence and likelihood that it can achieve the goals; 4) collect possible business models and strategies that enable tools to support the desired transition towards SFS.

CS coordinators trained by WP6 and WP7 leaders will do this via two workshops with business actors and three workshops with policy actors organized between month 16 (December 2023) and month 24 (August 2024).

The aim of the first policy workshop is to develop a shared understanding of the systemic barriers to transformation and to formulate ambitious but feasible SMART goals for the farming system.

The second policy workshop aims to collect possible measures and policy tools to support the selected goals.

The third policy workshop aims to combine goals and instruments into a policy mix and assess its coherence, consistency, and congruence and the likelihood that it can achieve the goals; revise if needed.

Whereas a guideline for the business workshops (T7.1) is yet to be delivered the aim of these workshops would be to collect and explore business models at the case level, and to identify potential end markets for SFS at the case level.

Within this envisioned policy environment (T6.1) we collect 1) possible business models and strategies tools to support the desired transition towards SFS; 2) identify end markets for sustainable products (T7.1).

The policy mixes, business models (T6.1 and T7.1), and insights on the interventions to be tested (T5.1) allow us to reconfigure the pre-existing networks and envision solutions to be tested.

3.1.1.3 Phase 3: synthesis

Phase three synthesizes the insights on the lock-ins and potential drivers, most promising behavioural interventions; policy design space where to intervene; possible business models and strategies, and the end markets for the products issued from SFS. An ex-ante systems dynamics model at the general scale (T2.3) is developed to do this. It builds on data from the cross-case analysis of food system mechanisms (T2.2) to produce the stock and flow diagrams.

Building on outputs from the Multi-Actor Approach (T9.3) and the stakeholder ecosystem mapping (T2.1), places to intervene in the systems will be identified in collaboration with the CS coordinators previously trained to envision systems mapping (T4.2). CS coordinators organize workshops to create systems and behavioural-based theories of change (ToCs). They build on the policy mixes and business models (T6.1 and T7.1), the identified lock-ins, levers (T2.2) and behavioural interventions on their CS scale (T3.1) as well as the behavioural factors identified on the country case scale (T3.2 and T3.3).

The ex-ante system dynamics model serves as the broader causal model to interlink and frame simulations and experiments (T2.3) conducted in the phase of iteration. Ex-ante systems dynamic model (T2.3) frames the interventions (both at case and general level). In contrast, the cross-case systems-based theory of change (T4.2) identifies policy, business and behavioural interventions at the general scale.

3.1.1.4 Phase 4: iteration

Phase four focuses on the **iteration**, which entails an additional round of sense-making activities (T5.2, T5.3, T5.4) and envisioning activities (T6.2 and T7.2).

In **each partner country** choice experiments (T5.2) targeting 200-500 farmers will be set up to test the effectiveness of the more generic farmer-targeted interventions emerging out of the ToC workshops. The ex-ante system dynamics model will provide the conceptual basis for the experimental design (T2.3).

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In five case studies (IE, BE-FL, CH, IT, FR) lab-in-the-field experiments (T5.3) with 20-30 farmers will be set up which will test case-study specific farmer-targeted interventions emerging out of the case-level ToC workshops. The ex-ante system dynamics model will provide the conceptual basis for the experimental design (T2.3).

Concurrently, a web-based tool to simulate the impact of the proposed interventions at the EU scale will be developed based on the ex-ante systems dynamics model (T2.3) and calibrated with the data available from the experiments (T3.3, T5.1, T5.2, T5.3). After a round of validation by a panel of stakeholders plus the EAB, the calibrated model will be embedded in a web-based user interface allowing citizens to elaborate on the effects of different scenarios across the EU.

The results of these experiments (and those of the nudge experiments from T5.1) and simulations will then be discussed in another set of participatory workshops first at the CS scale:

- One workshop in each CS (T6.2) to assess the capacity of the policy design space to implement the desired policies, re-evaluate the proposed designs and come up with strategies to enhance the intention and capacities for designing and implementing public policies at the local level.
- Three workshops/visits across cases (T7.2), each one focused on a new (type of) business model and one on market segmentation to improve the understanding of how to implement these new business models.
- And a workshop on strategies at the value chain level, of consumer behaviour and buying acts/market segmentation by farmers, so that they can better respond to changes in consumer demand.

And then, at the more general scale:

- A series of 3-5 online workshops at the general scale aiming at upscaling the transformative strategies with potential at the EU scale (T6.2).

Based on the CS reports on the process and outcome of the envisioning systems mapping workshops, MBS, EVILVO and NIBIO identify impactful interventions for further experimental research (choice experiments conducted in T5.2 and lab in the field experiments conducted in T5.3), to integrate into effective and implementable public strategies (T6.2) and effective and implementable private strategies (T7.2). Building from the case and cross-case ToCs (T4.2) we determine the case-level experiments (T5.3), the EU-scale-based experiments (T5.2) and simulated scenarios (T5.3).

3.1.1.5 Phase 5: (re)envisioning

Phase five, the **re-envisioning phase**, is the final phase of the ENFASYS project. It focuses on developing concrete propositions for the systemic change of farming systems. The objective of this phase is to bring together the findings and insights from earlier phases of the project and translate them into actionable recommendations for policy and practice.

In phase five, several key activities are carried out:

- **Impact assessment:** The impact of changes in the EU food system, based on the results of WP5 and the validated system-based theories of change (T4.3), is thoroughly discussed. This assessment aims to understand the potential effects and implications of the proposed interventions on the broader food system.
- **Synthesis of principles and lessons learned for public policies:** The principles and lessons learned from the research activities conducted in WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5 are synthesized. This synthesis aims to provide evidence-based recommendations on how public policies can effectively support the transition to sustainable farming systems.
- **Recommendations for private interventions:** Building on the outcomes of T7.1, T7.2, and the integrated findings from T4.2, recommendations are made on which private interventions are most effective for specific farming systems. These recommendations aim to help farmers overcome unsustainable lock-ins and adopt more sustainable practices.

By combining the insights from these activities, phase five provides a comprehensive understanding of the systemic changes needed in farming systems.

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The concrete propositions and recommendations developed in this phase serve as a roadmap for policymakers, practitioners, and other stakeholders, guiding their actions towards a just and fair transition to sustainable farming systems.

3.1.2 Processual account of the workflow: work packages

In this section we present the perspective of the CS coordinator and the WP leads on the work that needs to be done across research teams and case studies.

Each WP is presented with systems map that delineates the work it receives from and delivers to other WP and CS coordinators as well as the data collection and data analysis protocols in engages in to do so.

3.1.2.1 WP1 (FiBL): Scoping and Framing of pathways towards SFS

Figure 5 Methodological flow of WP1: what do they get from whom to do what and for whom

From the perspective of the coordinator WP1 focuses on scoping and framing pathways towards sustainable farming systems (SFS). This involves conducting state-of-the-art research and analysing ongoing projects to inform the direction of the ENFASYS project.

The goal is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research topic and guide the research activities within the project. WP1 plays a critical role in setting the scene conceptually and empirically for the other work packages. It provides the overarching framework and context for the research conducted in the project. Importantly the

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conceptual framework provides a common language for all consortium members, facilitating the coordination of internal exchanges.

From the perspective of the WP1 lead and co-leads the key tasks include firstly, scoping the research topic: this task involves conducting a thorough literature review and analysis of ongoing projects to identify the key issues, challenges, and research gaps related to sustainable farming systems (T1.1). This task focuses on developing a conceptual framework that defines key concepts, relationships, and objectives for the research conducted within the ENFASYS project.

The conceptual framework provides guidance on the overall direction of the project and helps align the work of different work packages. For this it uses a multilevel perspective (MLP) on sustainability transitions to link behavioural and systemic perspectives in a single narrative for ENFASYS. MLP identifies feedback loops and interactions across scales to understand dynamics and transition trajectories. As such it is applied to analyse systemic factors in SFS transitions. In ENFASYS it is specifically used to bridge the gap between behavioural and systemic factors, linking micro-level agency with macro level interactions.

This framework categorizes system elements into niches, regimes, and landscapes to study their interconnections. In ENFASYS it represents a central analytical tool to identify systemic factors and drive innovation. In addition to the MLP, the concept of three types of knowledge is used to distinguish different types of knowledge needed to generate change through a research project. The three types of knowledge are all needed to understand public and private interventions which have already happened in farming systems, as well as to inform the interventions design within ENFASYS to enable behavioural or systemic change.

Secondly, framing the pathways towards SFS (T1.2) aimed at developing a shared understanding among project partners. Gaining a common understanding within the ENFASYS consortium of transformation pathways means collating the ways in which the project partners think about transformation pathways in their individual contexts and identifying common and individual constructs.

We followed an approach based on personal construct theory by George Kelly to elicit project partners' personal constructs. In the second step, we analysed the constructs' relevance for transformation (by assessing the correlation with the construct "transformation potential"). The resulting structure was discussed in a validation workshop to which all partners were invited to attend. The consolidated structure of transformation pathways will serve as a tool to reflect on 1) potentially diverging understandings, 2) the characteristics of the pathways stimulated in case study work, and 3) the existence, or non-existence, of certain pathways in the ENFASYS project overall.

Thirdly, the Light Touch review (T1.3) informs the research direction by collecting and classifying relevant case studies from previous and ongoing EU and national projects to provide insights into the impact, successes, and failures of on-going and already implemented initiatives and to give project partners guidance for the contextualization of the selected ENFASYS case studies.

Initiatives were selected according to project partners' local knowledge and expertise on their domestic agrifood systems. In addition to meeting the definition of a transformation initiative, initiatives were eligible for inclusion on the condition that they directly or indirectly impact farming practice; have ambitions that go beyond the currently dominant farming practices and standards regarding climate, ecology, and social, and/or animal-welfare; and are either located in a European country or are a European-based branch/spin-off of a global initiative.

Each partner used a standardized questionnaire to conduct telephone interviews with real world transformation initiatives. A total of 101 case studies were analysed to identify and describe pathways, barriers, behavioural factors, and implemented interventions.

In combination, T1.2 and T1.3 provide a common understanding of transformation pathways that may be used by ENFASYS project partners in their CS work and by other researchers interested in facilitating transformation to SFS in other contexts. Overall, WP1 provides insights and recommendations based on the scoping and framing work to inform the research direction of the other WPs. This includes identifying research priorities, methodologies, and approaches that will be used throughout the project.

From the perspective of the CS coordinators, they are provided with guidelines from FiBL for T1.3, which involves conducting light touch reviews. These reviews consist of desk research and interviews, following the

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guidelines provided by FiBL. Each CS coordinator is required to map at least 10 initiatives. Further, CS coordinators participated at a one-to-one interview with FiBL to elicit personal constructs for T1.2.

Deliverable 1.2, which reports the findings from T1.2 and T1.3 is a tool for CS coordinators to map transition pathways to SFS of their CSs. CS coordinators are asked to research the goal framing in their case studies and place the case studies in the structure of pathways.

The objective is to: 1) gather insights on the success and failure of already implemented interventions and 2) contextualize and target the selected case studies of ENFASYS towards existing research gaps. This work is to be done by the CS coordinators with the support of FiBL.

3.1.2.2 WP2 (NIBIO): Developing a system dynamic understanding of mechanisms, lock-ins, and levers in the broader food system through CS research and scaling up to a system dynamic model for evaluation.

Figure 6 Methodological flow of WP2: what do they get from whom to do what and for whom

From the perspective of the coordinator WP2 develops an understanding of the food system dynamics which will be applied to a system dynamic model for ex ante evaluation. This enables an analysis of the factors that influence the adoption of sustainable practices, helping to create strategies for transitioning to a better food system.

From the perspective of the WP 2 lead and co leads the key tasks include conducting case studies of farming systems to analyse the transition process and identify lock-ins and potential levers for change. This is done using a multi-level (T2.1 and T2.2) and context sensitive dynamic model (T2.3) to capture the complex interplay of food systems actors' behaviour and their socio-cultural political and geographic context.

As such in T2.1 Mapping and surveying the stakeholder ecosystem, their perspectives and socio-cultural, economic and governance conditions (M6-20) data were collected from the case studies concerning value chain configurations, policy design space and governance environments; the perceived limitations and barriers to SFS along with cultural, economic, and environmental conditions that limit transition towards SFS, as well as enablers, that is the opportunities and promoting circumstances to transitioning.

T2.2 Developing a cross-case system dynamic analysis of food system mechanisms (M15-24) uses the structural equivalence analysis (Rocha et al. 2019) to develop a static picture of the overall farming systems across the case studies.

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Structural equivalence analysis is a method used to identify nodes in a network that play similar roles, allowing the identification of representative variables that belong to common structures. It involves examining the similarity of positions and connections between variables in a network, as well as their similarity across different cases. The analysis measures the Euclidean distance of variables in a directed graph and the Jaccard distance on a bipartite graph to approximate structural equivalence.

Hierarchical clustering is then used to group similar nodes based on their degree centrality in the combined network of causal loop diagrams (CLDs) or the cases they belong to. It does so in the form of CLDs that capture the feedback mechanisms that underlie systemic lock-ins as well as potential levers in every CS. By aggregating these identified relationships across the case studies based on the number of occurrences in each CS T2.2 develops a global system-based account of the food-system mechanisms.

T2.3 Building a general validated system dynamic model for ex-ante strategy assessment (M20 – M28) builds on the internal report of T2.2 to develop stock and flow diagrams aggregating data and results from the CS CLDs to assess the potential (cost) effectiveness of potential policy and business strategies at the CS and EU level.

From the perspective of the CS coordinators for the WP2 their work is steered first by UCL for the subtask 2.1 who develops a detailed data collection protocol to ensure consistency of methods across CSs. According to the protocol CSs conduct various data collection activities: literature review, interviews, focus groups, online surveys as presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Data collection overview for subtask 2.1. developed by UC Louvain (Antier and Baret, 2023)

As part of the work carried out in T2.2, NIBIO will develop an initial CLD for each CS based on the results of T2.1 and other secondary data. The initial CLD will then be refined with the CS coordinators through a bilateral meeting.

In order to facilitate the meeting, NIBIO will provide the CS coordinators in advance with a step-by-step procedure for building the CLD. The initial draft will then be developed into a final (validated) CLD through a workshop where stakeholders can interact and discuss the CLD.

An overview of the flow of activities for the preparation of a CLD for each CS in the months 15-22 is shown in Figure 8. After validation, the 10 CLDs will be aggregated by NIBIO, MBS, UCL and UNIBO using structural equivalence analysis.

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Figure 8 Timeline of the outputs for WP2

Finally, case studies will be asked to select experts who, together with JRC and EAB, will calibrate the stock and flow diagrams developed by UNIBO as part of T2.3 during the months 20-29.

3.1.2.3 WP3 (TEAGASC): Understanding behavioural factors in the decision making of farmers and the buying behavior of products from SFS

Figure 9 Methodological flow of WP3: what do they get from whom to do what and for whom

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From the perspective of the coordinator WP3 will identify a comprehensive set of behavioural factors that explain in general what influences farmers and consumer-citizens to move towards sustainable food systems. This groundwork is essential for developing targeted interventions, tailored to behavioural factors, to promote the transition to sustainable food systems.

From the perspective of the WP3 lead and co-leads the key tasks include conducting participatory workshops to identify different types of behaviour change interventions. The data from these workshops will inform the design of behavioural surveys with farmers. These surveys aim to investigate the behavioural readiness of farmers towards different intervention options, and the behavioural factors influencing readiness. This will provide evidence on how to align the design of interventions with target farmer behavioural profiles. Additionally, a behavioural survey of consumer-citizens will investigate their preferences and willingness to pay for more for SFS products, their preferences for alternative incentive schemes, and identify end markets based on market segmentation.

Interventions are categorized using either RESET Mindset Model or the behaviour change wheel (Lam et al. 2017). This categorization allows for comparisons to be made between case studies at the EU level. The RESET model is a systematic approach that classifies interventions based on the type of behaviour change interventions. The intervention categories include:

- **R:** rules and regulations. With this intervention type, the intended behavioural change is made compulsory, these interventions are not about “stimulating” but rather enforcing change.
- **E:** economics. With this type, either the intended behavioural change is made financially more attractive (e.g. price premium, subsidy), or ‘not changing behaviour’ is made financially less attractive (e.g. tax)
- **S:** social norms. With this type, we try to make the intended behaviour socially more attractive, for instance, by informing farmers how many other farmers in their reference group have already implemented the change, or by making not changing behaviour socially less attractive.
- **E:** education and information. Here we try to stimulate behavioural change by sharing information with farmers about why the behavioural change would be good, or how to implement the behavioural change, or why not changing behaviour would be bad.
- **T:** tools. Here we try to make the intended behavioural change materially more feasible or easier to implement or we make the ‘bad practice’ more materially difficult to maintain (e.g. by increasing administrative burden).

Overall, the RESET framework provides a systematic approach to categorize interventions based on their approach to behaviour change, allowing for comparisons to be made between different case studies.

Using the Self-regulated Stage model of Behaviour Change (SSBC) (Bamberg, 2013), each survey will examine one CS specific behaviour. The SSBC model consists of four stages: pre-decisional, pre-actional, actional, and post-actional .

- The first stage is the pre-decisional stage, where individuals have no plans to engage in the target behaviour and see no reason to do so or do not believe it is possible to adopt the new behaviour.
- The second stage is the pre-actional stage, where individuals are considering taking action but do not have a concrete idea of how to reach that goal yet.
- The third stage is the actional stage, where individuals have started planning how to implement the behaviour change, and know how to reach that goal, but have not started implementing this in everyday life.
- The final stage is the post-actional stage, where individuals have successfully adopted the behaviour change and are maintaining the new behaviour over time.

These stages provide a framework for understanding and analysing behaviour change processes and interventions in the context of the research study. They allow us to examine which interventions different farmer segments are willing to engage with and the behavioural factors which predict membership within segments. From this is we can create interventions targeted at segments and adapted to behavioural factors.

From the perspective of CS coordinators, the work for WP3, which is steered by TEAGASC, begins with the preparation of workshops for T3.1, which involves exploring the behavioural factors that influence the readiness of farmers for interventions related to sustainable farming systems (SFS). In this phase, CS coordinators identify the target population of farmers for whom quantitative evidence regarding barriers, levers, and the effectiveness of interventions needs to be produced. This includes determining the intended population of farmers for both the randomized trials in T5.1 led by UNIBO and the behavioural surveys conducted in T3.2.

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Once the target population is identified and the problem statement is defined, CS coordinators organize focus groups to define possible interventions that can stimulate changes in target behaviours. This preparation phase helps to inform the design of the survey conducted in T3.2, which aims to identify farmer behavioural factors towards interventions for SFS. During the behavioural survey, CS coordinators, with the support of TEAGASC, utilize the Self-Regulated model of Behaviour Change (SSBC) guidelines. Additionally, they design intervention vignettes with policy calibration in mind to ensure that the proposed interventions are realistic and align with the desired behavioural change goals.

3.1.2.4 WP4 (MBS): Develop systems- and behavioural based ToCs to understand the potential impact of public and private interventions

Figure 10 Methodological flow of WP4: what do they get from whom and to do what

From the perspective of the coordinator WP4 develops strategies based on theories of change to facilitate the transition towards SFS. To do so it focuses on understanding the current situation and identifying the necessary steps to achieve the desired sustainable food system.

This involves analysing behavioural and systemic factors that influence EU farming systems and identifying interventions that can drive positive change. Goal of WP4 is to create impact by integrating different types of results generated within the project and providing actionable strategies for transition towards SFS.

From the perspective of the WP4 lead and co-leads their key tasks include drafting an overarching methodological framework (T4.1) that guides the research conducted in the ENFASYS project by integrating different research perspectives using systems mapping. This framework focuses on the practical application of research methods.

In T4.2, they develop empirically grounded systems and behaviour-based Theories of Change (ToCs) across the case studies. This task builds on the structural equivalence analysis conducted by NIBIO and the results of the surveys on behavioural factors. The aim is to create a concept map that summarizes the key results of the systemic and behavioural research, identifying relevant places to intervene in the systems. Policy, business, and behavioural ToCs are developed at both the CS and European levels for further testing.

The ToCs are then translated into a systems map, which serves as a strategic toolkit for transformation. It identifies long-term goals and outlines the necessary conditions to achieve those goals. The map also maps out interventions that lead to the desired outcomes, identifies indicators for measuring progress, provides assumptions about the context

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of interventions, and illustrates the causal pathway linking interventions to possible outcomes. The ToCs also include a reflection on external and systemic factors that may influence the change process. Figure 10 presents the systems mapping process for drafting the ToCs.

Figure 11 Systems mapping in ENFASYS

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This work is done first at CS level and is co-designed with the CS coordinators. In a second step, the CS ToCs are disaggregated to identify patterns with the highest number of occurrences. These patterns are then aggregated into the European ToC, which cuts across scales based on policy, business and behavioural mixes, and provides guidance for the iteration phase of T6.2, T7.2 and T5.2.

Finally, (based on the results of the iterations in T4.2, T6.2 and T7.2), T4.3 focuses on developing validated system-level ToCs at the case and landscape levels. This task draws general lessons for formulating ToCs that are sensitive to local conditions and take into account feedback from the wider context and potential negative or unexpected consequences. It will be carried out from month 36 to month 44.

From the perspective of CS coordinators, the work for WP4, led by MBS, starts with training on how to create systems-based theories of change (ToCs) for their CS, building on the causal loop diagrams co-designed with NIBIO in WP2 during the months 20-21 (May/June 2024).

MBS will provide practical guidelines specifically tailored to each CS coordinator, considering the specifics of their empirical context. CS coordinators will then undergo collective training to organize participatory workshops during months 21-22.

By the end of month 25 (August 31st, 2024), CS coordinators will deliver a CS report on the processes and outcomes of these workshops to MBS and EVILVO. This report will outline the co-design process, including the shared understanding of lock-ins, the formulation of SMART goals for the farming system, and the identification of measures and policy tools to support the desired development. The report will also document the development of the policy mix, its assessment for coherence, consistency, congruence, and likelihood of achieving the set goals.

3.1.2.5 WP5 (UNIBO): Test the potential of systemic and behavioural interventions through experimental research and system dynamic modelling

Figure 12 Methodological flow of WP5: what do they get from whom and to do what

From the perspective of the coordinator WP5 focuses on conducting experimental research and system dynamic modelling to test the effectiveness of the co-created systems- and behavioural-based Theories of Change (ToCs) at CS level and beyond.

From the perspective of the WP5 lead and co-leads experiments and related system dynamic modelling unfold through four tasks from the envisioning to the (re)envisioning phase of the project (M15-40).

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1 T5.1, which focuses on randomized trials, aims to test the impact of different interventions on farmers' participation in voluntary schemes for sustainable food systems. The trials involve the same sample of farmers from T3.2 and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions such as information-based, education-based, and group pressure-based approaches. These interventions have been co-selected with EU-level policy makers, stakeholders, and the Joint Research Centre (JRC). The trials are pre-registered and aim to provide evidence on the effectiveness of the interventions in encouraging farmers towards sustainable farming practices.

T5.2 involves choice experiments that test the impact of policy interventions and retailers' strategies on farmers at a broad scale. The experiments offer different scenarios related to policy and business strategies and target a sample of farmers in partner countries with a minimum of 200 farmers per country. The goal is to provide evidence on the effectiveness of the tested interventions and strategies in promoting sustainable food systems. The results of these experiments are analysed by UNIBO and TEAGASC and presented in an internal report (M13) and a final report (D5.2), which includes lessons learned and best research practices for experimental approaches in sustainable food systems.

T5.3 involves lab-in-the-field experiments to test the impact of interventions at the case scale. These experiments simulate different real-life scenarios related to baseline scenarios, single type interventions, and theories of change. A non-hypothetical framed lab-in-the-field approach is used, incorporating a similar methodology with context-specific content provided by UNIBO. The results of these experiments provide evidence on the effectiveness of the tested interventions at the case level.

T5.4 focuses on the simulation of the impact of changes in the EU Food System using a system dynamic model. A web-based tool is developed to simulate the overall impact of tested interventions that stimulate the adoption of more sustainable behaviours. The model is calibrated using the results of the experimental research conducted in T3.2, T3.3, T5.1 and T5.2.

By completing these tasks, WP5 aims to test the potential of systemic and behavioural interventions through experimental research and system dynamic modelling. The results provide evidence on the effectiveness of different interventions and strategies.

From the perspective of CS coordinators, the work for WP5, led by UNIBO, and the work for WP3, led by TEGASC, have overlapping tasks in T5.1 and T3.1. In these tasks, CS coordinators are responsible for identifying the target population for whom quantitative evidence on barriers, levers, and the effectiveness of interventions needs to be produced.

For T5.2, CS coordinators will support UNIBO in finding a third party that will allow them to target a sample of at least 200 farmers per country. This task involves conducting choice experiments to test the impact of policy interventions and retailer strategies on farmers at a broad scale.

In T5.3, lab-in-the-field experiments will be conducted in Belgium, Italy, Switzerland, Ireland, and France. Each CS will involve 20-30 farmers and implement non-hypothetical framed lab-in-the-field experiments. Case study coordinators will be responsible for building lasting stakeholder engagement with the field to ensure sufficient levels of participation and engagement throughout the experiments.

For T5.4, CS coordinators will be asked to assemble a panel of stakeholders who will validate the system dynamic model of the impact of changes in the EU Food System.

By fulfilling these tasks, CS coordinators contribute to the overall objective of WP5, which is to test the potential of systemic and behavioural interventions through experimental research and system dynamic modelling. The collaboration between WP5 and the CS coordinators ensures that the interventions and strategies are effectively tested and verified in real-world settings.

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3.1.2.6 WP6 (HUB): Enhancing policy design and implementation for climate neutral and sustainable EU farming systems

Figure 13 Methodological flow of WP6: what do they get from whom and do to what.

From the perspective of the coordinator WP6 focuses on developing public policies that encourage farmers to transition towards more sustainable SFS. It involves a co-design process with stakeholders to create policy mixes that address specific lock-ins in farming systems.

From the perspective of WP leads and co-leads there are three key tasks within the WP6 that contribute to the overall goal of enhancing policy design and implementation for climate neutral and sustainable EU farming systems. During the process of these tasks, the focus switches from CS level to EU level.

Figure 14 WP6 Task interplay, levels, actions, and outcomes

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As shown in figure 14, the three consecutive tasks build on one another.

T6.1 involves the co-design of policy mixes to overcome lock-ins in the respective CSs. This task builds on the work done in WP1, WP2, and WP3 to develop guidelines and training for the co-design process with the CSs. The aim is to develop a shared understanding of the lock-ins in farming systems and formulate SMART goals for the desired development. Through a participatory process, relevant CS stakeholders will collect measures and policy tools to support the transition towards sustainable farming systems. The result will be a policy mix that is assessed for its coherence, consistency, congruence, and likelihood of achieving the jointly developed SMART goals.

T6.2 focuses on transformative strategies to implement policy designs at the CS level and beyond. Starting from the co-designed policy mixes developed in T6.1, this task aims to develop concrete strategies for implementing the policy mixes. The strategies will consider the specific context of each CS and consider scalability at a broader regional or national level (depending on the respective CS context), as well as the European level. The goal is to create effective implementation strategies that can overcome unsustainable lock-ins in farming systems. To this end, a list of strategies with potential to upscaling at EU-level will be produced in each CS during T6.2.

T6.3 is about developing design principles and lessons learned for public policies that help farming systems overcome unsustainable lock-ins. This task involves workshops and discussions with EU officials (relevant DGs and JRC) to analyse the outcomes and experiences of the policy design and implementation process. The goal is to extract generalizable lessons and design principles that can inform the development of public policies, both at EU level, as well as on more directly CS relevant levels. These lessons and principles will be valuable for future policy-making efforts aimed at promoting sustainable farming systems.

By completing these tasks, WP6 contributes to the overall objective of the ENFASYS project, which is to stimulate a just and fair transition to sustainable farming systems. The co-design of policy mixes and the development of transformative strategies ensure that public policies effectively address lock-ins and promote sustainable practices. The design principles and lessons learned provide valuable insights for policymakers to create policies that support the transition towards climate neutral and sustainable farming systems.

From the perspective of the CS coordinators, the work led by HUB unfolds through a series of training sessions and workshops.

In T6.1, the CS coordinators are trained to guide workshops to co-design policy mixes with stakeholders that can overcome lock-ins in the respective CSs. Through a participatory process, they will then organize a series of workshops for CS stakeholders to work together to develop a shared understanding of the lock-ins, formulate ambitious yet feasible SMART goals for the farming system, collect possible measures and policy tools to support the desired development, combine goals and instruments into a policy mix, and assess its coherence, consistency, congruence, and likelihood of achieving the set goals. Based on the workshop results, the CS coordinators will deliver a CS report describing the co-designed policy mix to HUB.

In T6.2, the CS coordinators will receive additional training on how to organize workshops with stakeholders to assess the capacity of the policy design space to implement desired policies, identify the need for change, and develop strategies that enhance the transition towards sustainable farming systems. They will then organize these workshops and deliver the CS report to HUB.

In T6.3., the CS coordinators will organize workshops with EU-officials (relevant DGs and JRC). They will draw from the previously developed list of policy strategies with potential for upscaling at EU-level to discuss with EU-officials. Jointly, they will elaborate policy design principles for future EU agricultural and food public policies.

By actively engaging stakeholders through these training and workshop activities, WP6 aims to enhance policy design and implementation for climate neutral and sustainable EU farming systems.

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3.1.2.7 WP7 (GAIA): Develop business strategies, models a social innovation that collectively incentivize farmers to move towards SFS

Figure 15 Methodological flow of WP7: what they get from whom and to do what

From the perspective of the coordinator WP7 focuses on creating business strategies and models to promote SFS, involving stakeholder co-design and exploitation of business strategies.

From the perspective of the WP7 lead and co-leads the work unfolds through three tasks from the envisioning to the (re)envisioning phase of the project (M16-48).

In T7.1, the focus is on identifying business models, strategies, and relevant end markets for sustainable products. This task involves studying existing business models and strategies, as well as exploring new and innovative approaches to promote sustainable farming systems. The goal is to identify effective models and strategies that can incentivize farmers to transition towards SFS.

In T7.2, the emphasis is on developing exploitation routes for the potential of evidence-based (new) business models and strategies of collaboration. This task involves working closely with stakeholders to co-design and refine the identified business models and strategies. The aim is to ensure that these models and strategies are practical, feasible, and have the potential to be implemented at scale.

Lastly, in T7.3, the focus is on generalizing the lessons learned from the development and implementation of business models and strategies. The goal is to extract key insights and best practices that can be applied more broadly to promote sustainable farming systems. These lessons learned will be shared with stakeholders and incorporated into the overall roadmap for transitioning to SFS.

Through these tasks, WP7 aims to contribute to the development and implementation of effective business models, strategies, and social innovations that collectively incentivize farmers to move towards sustainable farming systems.

From the perspective of the CS coordinators the work of WP7 the work of WP7 led by GAIA begins with training sessions to prepare them for organizing workshops that aim to achieve two objectives. Firstly, the workshops aim to collect possible business models and strategies that can support the desired transition towards sustainable farming systems (SFS). Secondly, they aim to identify end markets for sustainable products.

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These workshops, which are to be executed and reported between months 17 and 24, will be organized by CS coordinators with the support of GAIA and EVILVO. The focus of the workshops will be on two main aspects. Firstly, they will explore how to implement new business models and strategies at the value chain level. This involves identifying innovative approaches and solutions that can drive sustainable practices and engagement within the agricultural sector. Secondly, the workshops will delve into understanding consumer behaviour and buying patterns, as well as market segmentation by farmers. The objective is to enable farmers to better respond to changes in consumer demand and develop strategies to meet market needs effectively.

By organizing these workshops, CS coordinators will contribute to the overall goal of WP7, which is to develop business strategies, models, and social innovations that collectively incentivize farmers to transition towards SFS. The insights and outcomes from these workshops will inform the development and implementation of effective business models and strategies that align with the project's objectives.

3.1.3 Scalar perspective on the workflow

Beyond the processual equally important is the scalar perspective within the ENFASYS project. As pointed out in the ENFASYS conceptual framework (Ejderyan et al., 2023) the nature of the interconnected multiplicity of the system varies based on scale.

This means that the scale of the strategy, intervention or the model, and how it moves between scales will define the nature and the scope of systems change.

For example, the concept of agricultural systems includes the interactions between agricultural systems that act as drivers for change and operate on multiple scales, such would be agricultural systems with different agricultural objectives, the broader local and/or global environment, policies, institutions, markets and thus food systems (Skrimizea et al., 2020, p. 264 in Ejderyan et al. p. 39).

Therefore, in the case of ENFASYS we consider interventions and strategies from a macro, meso and a trans scalar perspective throughout the dynamic process of systems mapping.

Meso scale in the context of the ENFASYS projects refers to the farmers embeddedness in the landscape (W2, WP3, WP5). It encompasses the mapping of the policy mix at the CS level, focusing on how farmers can do policy implementation differently (T3.1). Likewise, it refers to strategies where we are observing from the perspective of the territory and the region, instead of focusing on a single company per se and their strategy.

Trans scalar in the context of ENFASYS project refers to actions and perspectives that cut across scales for the benefit of the SFS. In the context of the local actors this may be local coalitions operating within a specific territory that transcend their territorial locality to influence regional, national, or global value chains and policies (T7.2). It focuses on playing the scales by co-designing policy and business strategies (T6.1 and T7.1) by involving actors that operate at the national or EU case, considering the CSs in relation to national and EU policy frameworks and nationally or transnationally operating value chains.

Macro scale, in the context of the ENFASYS projects, refers to interventions and strategies that aim to influence the EU and national policies encompassing theories of change (T4.1 and T4.2), activities related to conceptual framing of the project itself (T1.1 and T1.2) and the activities that unfold in the (re)envisioning phase of the project with the scale to envision models, strategies and interventions for the large-scale transformation towards SFS (T4.3, T6.3, T7.3 and T5.4).

Figure 16 illustrates the scalar perspective by visually depicting the workflow's progression over time and across different scales. Each node is color-coded based on its corresponding phase (sensemaking - yellow outline; envisioning and iterating - green outline; synthesizing and re-envisioning – violet outline) and is clustered according to its temporal and scale characteristics.

The arrows represent the relationships between scales, demonstrating the scalar process of systems mapping.

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Figure 16 Scalar perspective on the ENFASYS workflow

4 Conclusion

ENFASYS's methodological brief uses systems mapping across different scales and levels of analysis to provide guidance on HOW to study the WHAT within the ENFASYS project.

The WHAT is provided by the ENFASYS conceptual framework, and the HOW is the systems mapping process across scales that outlines methodological approaches for analysing systemic and behavioural research, the testing and experimentation, the co-design of policies, and the engagement and exploitation of business strategies.

This methodological brief develops a processual account of systems mapping across scales to bridge the gap between systemic and behavioural methodologies, thus providing a common pathway across scales for actionable research towards sustainable farming systems. It does so by delineating five phases and three scales around which the research activities unfold, allowing them to speak to each other dialectically.

However, beyond this, the success of the ENFASYS project in enabling a just and fair transition to sustainable farming systems relies on the active engagement and collaboration of different actors within the project as outlined in the Multi-actor protocol. This includes the coordinator, WP leads, CS coordinators, and the stakeholders involved in the CSs. In that regard, the involvement of CS coordinators with stakeholders within their CSs is particularly important in ensuring the relevance and applicability of the research within specific contexts.

Close collaboration with stakeholders in the CSs allows for the co-creation and validation of theories of change, the identification of lock-ins and levers, and the design of interventions and strategies. This participatory process ensures that the research outcomes are context-specific and reflect the needs and perspectives of the stakeholders across scales.

The participatory dimension of systems mapping, which is outlined through the scalar perspectives across different levels of analysis, is critical for driving transformative change in the European Union Agri-Food Sector and achieving the objective of a just and fair transition to sustainable farming systems.

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